

Rice-based cropping systems

Economics of rainfed upland rice-based cropping systems in the northwestern Himalayas

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About 70% of 150,000-ha rice area in the Kumaon and Garhwal hills of Uttar Pradesh is in dryland rice. The most popular dryland 2-year rotation is rice (March-September) - wheat (October-May) - finger millet *Eleusine coracana* L. (June-October) - fallow (November-March). In this sequence, a 150% cropping intensity is obtained. Cropping intensity potential can be increased to 200% by direct seeding early-maturing rice varieties in June.

A 4-year fixed-plot field study at Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala (VPKAS) Experimental Farm, Hawalbagh (Almora), explored ways of increasing cropping system intensity. The local rotation was compared with five improved crop sequences, four of which used early-maturing experimental rice varieties.

Number of tillers, nitrogen concentration, and grain yield of kharif rice crops as influenced by dubari crops and nitrogen level

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Rice is the major kharif crop in Sind Province, Pakistan. Several rabi season dubari crops are cultivated after rice. Crop patterns are rice - gram, rice - lucerne, rice - fallow, and rice - wheat.

A study was conducted to determine the effects of dubari crops on number of tillers, percent nitrogen concentration, grain yield, and nitrogen response of the kharif crop. In the first-year study, gram - rice, lucerne - rice, fallow - rice, and wheat - rice were examined in a com-

Grain yield, costs, and returns 1977-78 to 1980-81 for dryland cropping systems in Uttar Pradesh, India.^a

Cropping pattern	Rainy season yield (t/ha)	Winter yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$+/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice - wheat	2.1	2.7	467	333	1.7
Rice - lentil	1.7	1.8	423	464	2.1
Rice - chickpea	1.9	2.2	457	711	2.6
Rice - pea	1.9	1.5	439	386	1.9
Spring rice - rapeseed	2.4	0.8	435	210	1.5
Spring rice - wheat	1.5	2.8	344	202	1.6
Finger millet - fallow	2.7				

^aCultivars used were VL206 (spring rice), experimental strains (June rice), VL421 (wheat), T36 (lentil), VL86 (chickpea), VL1 (pea), T9 (rapeseed), and VL101 (finger millet).

Average grain yield of June-seeded experimental varieties equaled that of spring-seeded rice. June seeding made 2 annual rice crops possible. Rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*), included in the spring sequence, produced a reasonably good yield (0.8 t/ha).

Highest average annual net return and benefit-cost ratios were recorded using a June-seeded rice - chickpea rotation followed by rice - lentil, rice - field pea, and rice - wheat sequences (see table). Results show that changing from tradi-

tional dryland rice rotations to more intensive cropping sequences using early-maturing varieties suitable for June seeding is profitable. Planting legumes in rabi season helps economize fertilizer use.

Improved cropping sequences provide a 2-week gap between harvest and seeding. Socioeconomic surveys indicate there is substantial underutilized human and bullock power in the hill villages to provide additional power requirements needed for more intensive crop rotations.

plete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 m × 10 m. No plot received nitrogen but all received 30 kg P₂O₅/ha. IR8 rice seedlings were transplanted.

In the second-year study 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha were tested in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Half of the nitrogen and 30 kg P₂O₅/ha were broadcast and incorporated into the soil. Remaining nitrogen was topdressed 30 days after transplanting (DT).

Number of tillers and percent nitrogen concentration at 30 DT, and grain yield (t/ha) of the rice crop increased progressively and significantly after gram and lucerne (see table). However, the rice crops did not differ significantly in those characteristics.

Effect of dubari crops on number of tillers and nitrogen concentration at 30 days after transplanting, and on grain yield of kharif rice;^a Sind, Pakistan.

Crop pattern	Tillers (no./hill)	N concentration (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Gram - rice	55 a	2.5 a	3.6 a
Lucerne - rice	52 ab	2.5 ab	3.5 ab
Fallow - rice	45 c	2.3 c	2.5 c
Wheat - rice	35 d	1.8 d	1.9 d

^aMeans followed by common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Yield after gram and lucerne increased with nitrogen levels up to 90 kg/ha, but decreased beyond that level (see figure). After wheat, yield increased with nitrogen levels up to 120 kg/ha, then declined. Maximum yields of rice